

Multilingual non-intrusive binaural intelligibility prediction based on phone classification

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Speech intelligibility prediction
Binaural
Non-intrusive
Deep neural network

ABSTRACT

Speech intelligibility (SI) prediction models are a valuable tool for the development of speech processing algorithms for hearing aids or consumer electronics. For the use in realistic environments it is desirable that the SI model is non-intrusive (does not require separate input of original and degraded speech, transcripts or *a-priori* knowledge about the signals) and does a binaural processing of the audio signals. Most of the existing SI models do not fulfill all of these criteria. In this study, we propose an SI model based on phone probabilities obtained from a deep neural net. The model comprises a binaural enhancement stage for prediction of the speech recognition threshold (SRT) in realistic acoustic scenes. In the first part of the study, SRT predictions in different spatial configurations are compared to the results from normal-hearing listeners. On average, our approach produces lower errors and higher correlations compared to three intrusive baseline models. In the second part, we explore if measures relevant in spatial hearing, i.e., the intelligibility level difference (ILD) and the binaural ILD (BILD), can be predicted with our modeling approach. We also investigate if a language mismatch between training and testing the model plays a role when predicting ILD and BILD. This point is especially important for low-resource languages, where not thousands of hours of language material are available for training. Binaural benefits are predicted by our model with an error of 1.5 dB. This is slightly higher than the error with a competitive baseline MBSTOI (1.1 dB), but does not require separate input of original and degraded speech. We also find that good binaural predictions can be obtained with models that are not specifically trained with the target language.

1. Introduction

Speech intelligibility is a crucial measure in human communication and is often affected by either extrinsic factors such as background noise, reverberation, competing speakers or by intrinsic factors such as hearing loss or cognitive factors. A common method to assess speech intelligibility of normal-hearing or hearing-impaired listeners are audiological tests using speech in noise. The masking noise is usually a stationary signal with the same long-term spectrum as the speech stimuli, as recommended by the International Collegium of Rehabilitative Audiology (ICRA) (Akeroyd et al., 2001). Usually, the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is adaptively adjusted so that the listener recognizes 50% of the words correctly. The corresponding SNR is referred to as the speech recognition threshold (SRT). Since performing audiological tests is time-consuming and generally requires lots of resources, accurate models that predict SI are desirable in the development of speech processing algorithms for hearing aids or consumer electronics.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csl.2024.101684>

Received 26 May 2023; Received in revised form 7 June 2024; Accepted 29 June 2024

Available online 3 July 2024

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Fig. 1. Overview of the speech intelligibility models mentioned in the introduction and their relationship to each other. The light gray circles show the principles on which the models are based: signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), correlation, Gaussian mixture model (GMM), hidden Markov model (HMM), neural network (NN), equalization and cancellation (EC) and better-ear glimpsing. The white boxes display the models that require clean speech signals, the gray boxes show the models that do not require clean speech signals but use word labels and the black boxes highlight the non-intrusive models.

Several existing models are introduced in the following paragraph. An overview of these models and their relationship to each other is displayed in Fig. 1. A well-known approach for such a prediction is the speech intelligibility index (SII) (ANSI, 1997), that is based on the articulation index (AI) (ANSI, 1969). The SII is the weighted sum of the SNRs over different frequency bands and results in values between zero (only noise, speech is unrecognizable) and one (no noise, the speech is completely recognizable). However, this value is not identical to SI, so the SII needs to be mapped to a reference condition measured with human listeners in order to predict the SRT. The SII uses the long-term spectrum of signals to calculate the frequency dependent SNRs and therefore cannot account for temporal modulations (Rhebergen and Versfeld, 2005). To solve this problem, the SII was extended (ESII) (Rhebergen et al., 2006) by analyzing the signals in short time steps. The short-time objective intelligibility measure (STOI) (Taal et al., 2011) can also deal with modulations in the time domain by using the signal envelopes. The SI predictions are based on the cross correlation between the envelopes of the clean speech and the degraded speech (e.g., speech mixed with noise); a high correlation should correspond to a high SI performance. The extended STOI (ESTOI) (Jensen and Taal, 2016) also considers spectral modulations in the frequency domain by calculating the spectral correlation between clean and degraded speech.

An approach for perception modeling based on automatic speech recognition (ASR) has been pursued in several studies: The glimpsing model (Cooke, 2006) uses a Gaussian mixture model (GMM) in combination with a hidden Markov model (HMM) to recognize the speech by considering only the spectrogram patches above the noise floor. Therefore, the model requires separated speech and noise signals and additionally the true word labels to calculate the word error rate (WER). A different GMM-HMM-based model that can be used for SI prediction is the framework for auditory discrimination experiments (FADE) (Schädler et al., 2016, 2018). The model can accurately predict SI, but it uses the same speech signals in training and testing, which can be interpreted as a classifier with a priori knowledge that is not available in real-world scenarios. Spille et al. (2018) proposed a model using a deep neural network (DNN) in combination with an HMM, which works with independent speech signals in training and testing. The model – which we will refer to as *Spille18* – can accurately predict SI for normal hearing (NH) listeners, but it was trained and tested using identical noise signals for masking and requires the true word labels to calculate the WER. This model was extended to incorporate a hearing loss for predicting SI for hearing-impaired (HI) listeners (Roßbach et al., 2022). This extension is referred to as deep ASR for intelligibility (DAILY). DAILY was trained and tested with different speech signals as well as very similar, but different noise signals to avoid overfitting. DAILY can predict SI for NH and HI listeners, but still requires the true word labels and is trained in matched conditions.

To predict intelligibility of noisy signals with unknown spoken content, non-intrusive (or blind) models are desirable. Non-intrusive in this context means that the model receives only the mixed signal and has no *a-priori* knowledge about the signals, i.e., neither the speech nor the noise was included in the model optimization and no additional information about the test signal (e.g., a transcript or the noise type) is used as model input. To predict the SI of degraded speech signals, a non-intrusive extension of the STOI (NI-STOI) was developed (Andersen et al., 2017). Instead of requiring the clean speech as input, NI-STOI estimates the clean speech envelopes from the degraded speech signal. The model can predict the SI for different noise types except for competing speakers, since in this case the clean speech estimator cannot distinguish between speech and noise. The twin-HMM-based STOI also predicts the SI by estimating the clean speech signals from noisy speech files (Karbasi et al., 2016). The estimation of the clean speech signals is performed by a forward-backward algorithm using the true word labels and the features extracted from the noisy speech signals with noise-matched training and testing. It is however not reference free since a model prediction requires the comparison of transcript and the true word labels which are not available in real-world scenarios. A GMM-HMM system is trained and tested with speech from different speakers to predict the SI in quiet of elderly, hearing-impaired listeners (Fontan et al., 2020). The model achieves high correlations between the predicted and measured SI but also produces high root mean squared errors (RMSEs). ASR-based models can also be designed as non-intrusive approaches: Another model combines an ASR-based system with

various types of signal-based SI predictions (Karbasi et al., 2020). To predict the percentage of correctly recognized words, these SI predictions were mapped to the results of listening experiments by using a binary classification neural network.

All these models can predict SI only for monaural signals, but SI strongly relies on binaural hearing in most everyday situations (Koenig, 1950). The Equalization and Cancellation (EC) model (Durlach, 1963) can be used to simulate this binaural processing: By equalizing the level and phase of the two channels of a stereo signal and subsequent canceling of the noise by adding or subtracting the equalized channels, a mono signal with improved SNR can be produced. The decision whether to add or subtract the equalized channels is made based on the SNR of the individual frequency bands. A modified version of the EC model was used to develop a deterministic binaural STOI (DBSTOI) (Andersen et al., 2016). The stereo signals of the clean speech and the degraded speech are combined into mono signals by an EC stage, which is followed by an envelope extraction similar to regular STOI processing. The parameters of the EC stage are chosen to maximize DBSTOI. At low SNRs, this leads to a signal-dependent bias, especially for uncorrelated stimuli. To solve this problem, a modified DBSTOI (MBSTOI) was developed (Andersen et al., 2018). The MBSTOI can accurately predict the SI in multiple different spatial scenes, but requires the clean speech signals in addition to the degraded signals. Another binaural prediction model that also uses an EC stage is the binaural speech intelligibility model (BSIM) (Beutelmann and Brand, 2006). BSIM combines a gammatone filterbank with an EC stage and provides a monaural signal that can be used as input to a monaural SI backend such as the SII (BSIM+SII). Since the decision of whether to add or subtract the equalized channels is based on the SNR of each frequency band, the speech signal and noise signals are required as separate inputs to BSIM.

To deal with mixed noisy speech signals, a non-intrusive (or blind) advancement of BSIM (bBSIM) (Hauth et al., 2020) was developed. Instead of calculating the SNR with separated signals, the SNR is estimated by using the speech-to-reverberation modulation energy ratio (SRMR) (Santos et al., 2014). To obtain a non-intrusive prediction with this approach, bBSIM was combined with a binaural phone-based prediction of speech intelligibility (BAPSI) (Roßbach et al., 2021). The backend first computes the phone probabilities over time for the monaural output of bBSIM. Then, an entropy measure is used to calculate the similarity of the phone probabilities over time. Since phone probabilities degrade (or smear) over time in the presence of noise, a higher similarity corresponds to a lower entropy as well as a lower predicted SI. Since the numerical values of the entropy-based measure are not identical to the percentage of speech correctly understood, a single reference condition is required to map these values to speech intelligibility scores. For the conditions analyzed in Roßbach et al. (2021) (anechoic chamber, office and cafeteria with different azimuth angles of the noise source), the prediction accuracy of BAPSI is similar to the intrusive baseline BSIM but depends on the spatial scene: For the anechoic chamber, the RMSE of BAPSI is lower (0.6 dB) than that of BSIM (1.8 dB), the RMSEs of the office room are similar with 0.8 dB (BAPSI) and 0.5 dB (BSIM), and the RMSEs in the cafeteria are higher for BAPSI (2.1 dB) than for BSIM (0.3 dB). This could be due to signal distortions generated by the EC-based frontend that negatively affect the backend, which could be avoided by a binaural stage integrated in the phone-based approach.

Instead of using an EC stage to combine a binaural audio signal into a monaural signal, a better-ear glimpsing can also be used (Brungart and Iyer, 2012). For this purpose, the left and right signal are divided into time-frequency (TF) regions with a duration of 10 ms and an equivalent rectangular bandwidth of 0.2. For each TF region, the corresponding part of the left and the right signal are compared and the part with the lower overall masking energy is used for the enhanced monaural signal. In listening experiments, the enhanced monaural signals lead to similar SI than the binaural signals.

This study introduces a non-intrusive and phone-based prediction model with a binaural integration stage, inspired by better-ear glimpsing. The model is referred to as PHOne-based Binaural Intelligibility model (PHOBI). Our study is comprised of two parts that explore speech-in-noise intelligibility: Part I compares model predictions with subjective scores collected in different simulated rooms and target-masker configurations from 10 normal-hearing listeners. Part II addresses binaural effects and cross-lingual aspects of the model based on subjective data from 25 NH listeners: To quantify the model properties beyond simple better-ear-listening (which is used in most of the binaural SI models, but not in human listeners), we explore if intelligibility level differences (ILD) and binaural ILD (BILD) can be predicted using a binaural integration scheme. Since the results of Part I show that a model trained with English can also be used to predict the SI of German utterances, we also wanted to investigate the effect of different test languages. To this end, scores from subjects listening to a speech-in-noise test in their respective first language (German, Swedish, British) are compared and analyzed.

2. Methods

The study contains two different experiments and is therefore divided into two parts. Part I of the study deals with the binaural SI in three different room conditions with a speaker at 0 degrees azimuth and a noise source positioned at varying azimuth angles. Part II of the study investigates whether a monolingual model can be used for multilingual predictions of the SI benefit of binaural listening by using three different languages. The model including the binaural integration stage as well as the SRT prediction is similar in both parts and is explained together. An overview of the model is shown in Fig. 2. The stimuli, listening experiments and the baseline models differ in both parts and are therefore explained separately.

2.1. Phone classifier

The block II.A in the lower part of Fig. 2 shows the monaural phone classifier of the prediction model. First, amplitude modulation filterbank features (AMFB) (Moritz et al., 2015b,a, 2016) are extracted from the audio signals and used as input for the DNN, as these features lead to accurate SI predictions for speech mixed with different modulated maskers (Spille et al., 2018). AMFB features

Fig. 2. Illustration of the PHOne-based Binaural Intelligibility model (PHOBI). The model is based on an ASR system (lower branch, Label II.A) trained with open-source databases. Predictions are obtained by extracting phone probabilities and estimate the word error rate (WER) from them (II.B). Subjective scores are collected in virtual acoustic scenes (II.C and II.D), which are compared to an estimated SRT (II.E). Box labels correspond to the according subsections in this paper.

include the decomposition of the audio signal into amplitude modulated sub-band frequency components to provide a representation of the temporal modulation frequencies. The next step is the DNN, which returns the probabilities of phones over time. The resulting 2D activation plot is referred as posteriorgram (pgram). To obtain accurate pgrams in different noise situations, the DNN is trained in a supervised fashion as part of an ASR system then combines DNN and an HMM. The system is trained with labeled, noisy speech material. The initialization and the training of the DNN-HMM hybrid system is carried out with the Kaldi toolkit from Povey et al. (2011) and the training recipe of Veselý et al. (2013). The HMM is initialized with a GMM-HMM baseline system. The training of the HMM language model is based on the training labels. For the DNN initialization stacked restricted Boltzmann machines are used. The HMM is necessary during training to transfer the phone probabilities of the DNN output into a transcript, but it remains unused when the trained model is applied (the model itself therefore does not require word labels to produce predictions). The minimization of the cross-entropy between this transcript and the labels is the aim of the optimization of the DNN weights and is done by using stochastic gradient descent. The DNN training is carried out with an adopted learning rate and results in a fully connected feed-forward DNN with seven hidden layers and 2048 neurons per layer.

The audio signals for the training should be different from the testing material to receive an independent system. Therefore, the LibriSpeech corpus (Panayotov et al., 2015) with 960 h of English audiobooks is used for the ASR training. Each speech signal is randomly mixed with one of 33,000 noise tracks of the BBC sound effects database (BBC, 2022) at a random signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) in a range of -10 to 20 dB SNR. The BBC database contains different kinds of sounds from nature, human produced sounds, machine sounds, animals, industry and much more (but no stationary speech shaped noise as used for testing the model).

Together with the binaural integration stage, the phone classifier should be used for binaural predictions in different acoustic scenes, so it is important to train the ASR-system with signals containing spatial information. Therefore, the speech and noise files are convolved with room impulse responses (RIR) from the Aachen Impulse Response Database (AIR) (Jeub et al., 2009, 2010) before they are mixed together. AIR contains RIR from one lecture room, one meeting room, one stairway, one corridor and the Aula Carolina (comparable with a small church). To obtain a general model, the direction of the speech and the noise is randomized. The output of the DNN is one pgram with the activations of 39 phones, one non-speech noise (NSN) and one silence activation over time.

2.2. Binaural integration stage

The key idea of the binaural integration stage is to extract acoustic information that goes beyond simple better-ear listening. The main processing steps are to identify a better ear and then further improve this representation by using information from the worse ear. For the prediction of SI, the signal parts that contain speech are most informative. The first step of this post-processing stage is therefore to exclude output vectors from the neural net that contain non-speech noise or silence, both of which are output classes of the network; output vectors for which either of these classes has the highest value are excluded.

Fig. 3. Processing steps for combining two monaural posteriorgrams into a binaural enhanced representation P^{bin} . After defining a better (P^b) and a worse (P^w) posteriorgram, they are combined into a new one (\hat{P}). The noisy time-phone bins $[p_N, n_N]$ are used to suppress the phonetic noise.

The DNN produces phone probabilities for single-channel input only. To obtain binaural predictions, signals from the left and right ear are processed separately and then used as input in the binaural integration stage as illustrated in Fig. 3 and motivated by a better-ear glimpsing (Brungart and Iyer, 2012). The general idea behind this processing step is to first pick the pgram that represents the better ear and subsequently further improve this representation with information from the worse ear for selective suppression of noisy phones.

The first step of the integration process is to quantify the difference between pgrams for each processed channel (Fig. 3 I). For very similar representations, we assume binaural differences to be very small and choose an arbitrary channel output without further processing (Fig. 3 II). To quantify the difference, we first determine the ratio of reliable and unreliable frames for the left and right pgram separately. A phone frame is categorized as reliable if it contains at least one clear phone activation that exceeds the threshold Θ defined as ten times the chance probability, i.e., $\Theta = 10 \cdot p_c$ with $p_c = 1/41$ (the latter value was chosen since the system produces 41 phone classes). If these ratios are relatively similar, i.e., their absolute difference is smaller than p_c , further binaural processing is skipped as mentioned above. Otherwise, the pgram with the higher ratio is used as better ear pgram (P^b) and the other one as worse ear pgram (P^w) (Fig. 3 III). After this decision, the worse ear is used to find the noisy phones p_N , i.e., the phones for which a larger portion of the activations over time can be attributed to noise (Fig. 3 IV). For each phone class, the number of frames with activations between p_c and Θ are counted. This number is then divided by the number of pgram frames to obtain the low activation ratio for each phone. If this ratio is larger than the frequency of occurrence of the most present phone /n/ (which is 0.0540 for American English (Greenberg et al., 1996)), the phone is defined as noisy.

In the next step, both pgrams are combined to \hat{P} (Fig. 3 V). The spatial difference between the two ears results in a time difference between the two audio signals. To combine the two signals, they are usually aligned with each other. In the case of combining the pgrams, an alignment is not necessary because the maximum time difference between the ears of 1 ms (for a typical distance of 0.34 m between the ears and $340 \frac{m}{s}$ sound velocity) is small compared to the 10 ms analysis blocklength of the pgrams. Even if one ear is generally classified as the better ear, phone recognition on the worse ear may be better in individual time frames due to signal modulations caused by spatial influences or modulated noises. Therefore, the pgrams from both ears are combined into \hat{P} by taking the phone vector with the highest maximum activation for each frame.

In the next step, our aim is to exploit binaural information for suppressing phonetic noise (noisy phone activations). In preliminary experiments, we found that the simple strategy of choosing the minimum value for noisy phones results in phone representations that overestimate the binaural effect. We therefore implement a gradual remixing that still considers information from both ears with the aim of reducing noisy time-phone activations.

This remixing affects only the noisy time-phone bins, so the respective time bins n_N must be found in the noisy phone vectors (Fig. 3 VI). For each vector p_N of \hat{P} , the time bins n_N smaller than Θ are determined.

After that, we calculate the absolute difference between $P^b[p_N, n_N]$ and $P^w[p_N, n_N]$ for each noisy time-phone bin (Fig. 3 VII). If this difference is small, i.e., below the chance probability p_c (2.4%), we assume that binaural effects do not play a major role for this specific segment and the value of \hat{P} remains unchanged. Otherwise, the current activation is scaled with $\frac{P_l[p_N, n_N]}{P_h[p_N, n_N]}$, where h denotes the element with the higher value (higher noise level) and l represents the lower value (lower noise level). This mechanism will therefore only lower activation values that have been identified as noisy according to the previous processing steps and should act as binaural denoising stage (Fig. 3 VIII). The larger the difference between the better and the worse ear, the stronger the noise reduction. The result is a binaural enhanced pgram (P^{bin}) (Fig. 3 IX). A high SNR leads to clear phone activations, while a low SNR leads to many small and uncertain phone probabilities. Therefore, entropy-based measures applied to the phone representation could be used to predict SI. We use the MTD (Hermansky et al., 2013) which can be used to calculate the similarity of phone vectors over time (Huber et al., 2018). The MTD is given by

$$M[\Delta n] = \frac{1}{N - \Delta n} \sum_{n=\Delta n}^N D[\bar{p}[n - \Delta n], \bar{p}[n]] \quad (1)$$

where D is the symmetric Kullback–Leibler divergence (or relative entropy) and $\bar{p}[n]$ and $\bar{p}[n - \Delta n]$ are phone vectors with the time difference of Δn . To avoid non-numerical results from this operation which involves logarithmic expressions, phone probabilities with a value of zero are replaced with the machine precision (in this case 2^{-52}). To take into account different temporal phone distances, the mean MTD \bar{M} is obtained (and used as final model output value) by averaging the MTD M of different Δn values from 350 to 800 ms. By choosing this range, effects from co-articulation (in the range up to 200 ms) are excluded.

Table 1

Overview of the male (m) and female (f) speech signals, noises and head-related transfer functions (HRTFs) for Part I and II of the study. Model training data is disjoint from these data sets and not listed in the table.

Audio signals		HRTFs used for:	
Matrix sentences	Noise	Measurements	Predictions
Part I	German (m) (Wagener et al., 1999)	olnoise (m) (Wagener et al., 1999)	anechoic (Algazi et al., 2001) office (Beutelmann and Brand, 2006) cafeteria (Beutelmann and Brand, 2006)
Part II	German (m) (Wagener et al., 1999) British (m) (Hewitt, 2008) Swedish (f) (Wagener, 2004)	ICRA1 (m) (Dreschler et al., 2001) ICRA1 (f) (Wagener et al., 2007)	anechoic (unknown source) anechoic (Kayser et al., 2009)

2.3. Stimuli

For an easier comparison of the two study parts, the stimuli of both parts are listed in Table 1.

2.3.1. Stimuli part I

The audio signals used for study part I were taken from the Oldenburg Sentence Test (OLSA) (Wagener et al., 1999; Wagener and Brand, 2005). The OLSA is a matrix test that combines 50 German words of five different categories to sentences with the structure <name><verb><number><adjective><object> (e.g., "Thomas gibt acht schwere Ringe"/"Thomas gives eight heavy rings"). The ten words per category are combined into 120 5-word sentences, which are optimized with respect to similar intelligibility. To mask the speech signals, a noise was generated with the same long-term spectrum as the speech signals (which is referred to as olnoise and is the standard masker in speech audiometry with this test).

To create stereo signals containing binaural information, the monaural signals are convolved with head-related transfer functions (HRTFs). The HRTFs were measured in three different room conditions: anechoic, office and an empty cafeteria. The anechoic HRTFs are part of an open-source HRTF database (Algazi et al., 2001) and were measured using a KEMAR manikin. The HRTFs of the office and the empty cafeteria were recorded with a B&K manikin for different azimuth angles (Beutelmann and Brand, 2006).

2.3.2. Stimuli part II

To investigate whether a monolingual model can be used for multilingual predictions, the British (Hewitt, 2008) and Swedish matrix tests (Wagener, 2004) (based on the matrix test Hagerman (1982)) were used in Part II in addition to the German matrix test. The speech signals of each of the three languages were masked with the ICRA1 noise (Dreschler et al., 2001), which is an unmodulated speech-shaped noise. For each language, either the ICRA1 with male or female frequency characteristics was chosen depending on the sex of the speaker (male weighted spectrum: high-pass 100 Hz 12 dB/Oct; female weighted spectrum: high-pass 200 Hz 12 dB/Oct). Since the HRTFs used in the listening experiments to simulate binaural signals in an anechoic room were not available, the predictions of Part II were done with HRTFs measured by Kayser et al. (2009). However, since the acoustic scenario is an anechoic room, the different HRTFs should have very little effect on the results.

2.4. Listening experiments

The performance of the model was evaluated through two distinct listening experiments, detailed in the subsequent subsections. The first experiment aimed to assess the model's capability in predicting SI across various directions of arrival of noise sources within different spatial acoustic environments. The second experiment aims to measure the model's accuracy in predicting the binaural benefit that extends beyond the capabilities of better-ear listening. Additionally, this experiment provides an opportunity to assess the model's ability to accurately predict the SI in a language not included in its training dataset, thereby testing its generalization and applicability across linguistic boundaries. Therefore, the listening experiments of both study parts were performed with matrix tests in different languages. The subjects listened to 5-word sentences mixed with noise and were asked to repeat the words they understood. Depending on their answer, the SNR of the next sentence was adaptively adjusted to obtain a recognition rate of 50%, the noise level was fix at 65 dB SPL.

2.4.1. Listening experiments part I

The SRT measurements of Part I were performed by Beutelmann and Brand (2006) with ten NH subjects (age: 21–43 years). The subjects listened to the German OLSA sentences mixed with the stationary olnoise. The target speaker was located at 0° in front of the listener. The direction of the noise source was varied with different azimuth angles from -135° to +180° and a distance of 1.45 m to the listener. Binaural SI is highly influenced by the direction of arrival of the target and the noise source. To avoid measurement errors due to head movements, the subjects listened to the mixed signals via Sennheiser HDA200 headphones in an isolated sound booth. The spatial acoustic scenes were generated by using HRTFs (measured with a KEMAR manikin for the anechoic room and a B&K 4128C manikin for the other rooms).

2.4.2. Listening experiments part II

The SRT measurements of Part II were carried out with NH listeners from three different countries (Wagener et al., 2007; van Esch et al., 2013; Van Esch and Dreschler, 2015). Each of the five German, five Swedish and 15 British subjects performed the matrix test in their native language. The measurements were carried out with free-field equalized Sennheiser HDA200 headphones using HRTFs of an anechoic room to simulate a binaural free-field condition as explained in Section 2.3.2. To investigate the SRT benefit of binaural listening, three different combinations of speech and noise source angles were measured by using the corresponding HRTFs. The condition with speech and noise co-located at 0° (SON0) was used as reference for the benefit of spatial listening. The SRTs were additionally measured with the speech source at 0° and the noise source at 90° from the left or right ear (SON90). The difference between the SRT of SON0 and SON90 is known as the intelligibility level difference (ILD). To obtain the binaural benefit of this spatial source separation, the SON90 condition is measured twice, i.e., monaurally with the noise source on the contra-lateral side (which corresponds to better-ear listening) and binaurally (which results in an additional benefit and hence *lowered* SRTs). The difference between the monaural and the binaural measurement is referred as binaural intelligibility level difference (BILD). For each subject, the ILD and BILD were determined twice with the noise source on the left and right side for the first and second measurement, respectively. Additionally, all subjects (except for three British listeners) performed the measurements twice at different times.

2.5. Prediction of the speech recognition threshold with PHOBI

To predict the SRT, we use sentences with different SNRs as model input and observe the corresponding outputs and effectively sample the psychometric function of the model. The SNR of the point of inflection of this function is used as SRT. In preliminary experiments, we observed an offset (in terms of the SNR) between the average psychometric function of NH listeners and the psychometric function from the model. For the experiments in Part I of this paper, this offset is compensated based on data of a single acoustic reference condition that is not part of the later evaluation: 100 OLSA sentences produced by a female speaker masked with the stationary olnoise and without any spatial information were used to calculate the reference psychometric function of the model. The offset with respect to NH SRT scores (Wagener et al., 1999) is applied to the model outputs in Part I, in which 20 different sentences produced by a male speaker (in different spatial acoustic scenes) are used for the evaluation. For experiments in Part II of this study, only *relative* differences between SRTs or psychometric functions are relevant. Hence, an offset correction is not required. One important parameter in this procedure is the number of utterances used to sample the psychometric function, which is explored separately in the following subsection and in Section 3.1. The result of the sub-study is anticipated here since it is used for the SRT predictions, which are based on 140 different SNRs between -40 and 20 dB and 10 utterances per SNR.

2.6. Sampling of the psychometric function

In this section, we explore the interaction between the number of utterances used for sampling the psychometric function of the model and the model's SRT accuracy. A lower number of utterances (or SNRs which are used in the sampling procedure) is desirable since it reduces the computational cost of predicting SI. On the other hand, stable SRT predictions can only be obtained if the across-sentence variability is reflected in the sampling process. The sampling of the psychometric function was investigated independent of the other predictions in this study. Therefore, we used monaural female German OLSA sentences and the corresponding noise, i.e., speech signals that are not used for the predictions that are presented later. The 120 sentences are mixed with the noise at each of 400 equally distributed SNRs between -40 and 20 dB SPL. Afterwards, the SRT is calculated for each combination of one to ten random utterances per SNR and five to 400 random SNRs (in steps of five). To obtain a statistically meaningful result, a bootstrapping with 1000 repetitions is performed. The aim of this step is to determine a compromise between SNR resolution, number of utterances per SNR and the predicted SRT. To this end, the accuracy of the predictions is measured in terms of root mean squared error (RMSE) between each SRT and the SRT obtained with the highest number of SNR classes (400) and sentences per SNR (10) used in this paper.

2.7. Baseline models

To evaluate the SRT predictions of the proposed model, the results of both parts of our study are compared with different baseline models. The functionality of each model is explained in the following paragraphs.

2.7.1. Baseline models part I

The data from the listening experiments used in this part have already been applied in other publications (Beutelmann and Brand, 2006; Roßbach et al., 2021; Hülsmeier et al., 2021) to verify the prediction accuracy of SI models. To increase comparability between different studies, these three models are included here as baselines.

The first model is the BSIM combined with the SII as backend (BSIM+SII) (Beutelmann and Brand, 2006). In this approach, speech and noise signals are processed separately for two reasons: BSIM requires an accurate frequency-dependent SNR calculation for the binaural enhancement and the SII requires separate speech and noise signals to predict the SRT. First, speech and noise signals from the left and right channel are first passed to a gammatone filterbank. Afterwards, correlated noise components are attenuated by an equalization and cancellation (EC) stage. The EC stage includes an artificial processing error to model human inaccuracy (Durlach, 1963). The SII backend uses the binaurally enhanced speech and noise signals as input and calculates an index

between 0 and 1. To predict an SRT, the SII needs to be mapped with a reference SRT measurement, which in this case is the SON0 condition (speech and noise from 0° in front of the listener) in the anechoic room.

The second baseline model BAPSI (Roßbach et al., 2021) uses an extension of the original BSIM as frontend, i.e., the bBSIM (Hauth et al., 2020). The bBSIM is a blind version of the BSIM and can process mixed speech and noise signals since it predicts the SNR based on the speech to reverberation modulation ratio (SRMR) (Santos et al., 2014). The model backend is based on a DNN that was trained as phone classifier as part of a hybrid ASR system. The ASR system, combining a DNN and Hidden Markov model (HMM), was trained with 10 h of read OLSA sentences from 20 different speakers (10 female, 10 male) (Meyer et al., 2015). The speech files were mixed with noise at SNRs from -10 to 20 dB to obtain 80 h of training data. Note that the HMM was only used while training the model, while it is not required to obtain model predictions. These are calculated from the DNN phone probabilities, which are subject to the mean temporal distance. This is the same approach as for the PHOBI model, which is explained in Section 2.2. The arbitrary values from the mean temporal distance need to be mapped to SRT values, which in this case is done with data from an SON0 listening condition in an anechoic room (which is the same condition as for the BSIM+SII model). Note that the utterances for learning this mapping are not used for any predictions presented in this study.

The third baseline model is bBSIM+FADE (Hülsmeier et al., 2021). The model uses the same frontend as BAPSI which is combined with FADE (Schädler et al., 2015) as backend. The speech mixed with noise at different SNRs is used as binaural input to bBSIM and the enhanced monaural output is passed to FADE. FADE comprises a GMM in combination with an HMM to produce transcripts of the input sentences that are later compared to the true word labels. The feature extraction stage uses separable Gabor filterbank features (SGBFB) (Schädler and Kollmeier, 2015) which are calculated from the mel spectrograms of input signals. The FADE approach requires many GMM/HMM systems to be trained at a specific SNR. For each SNR (-24 dB to 6 dB in 3-dB steps), training is performed with 960 labeled noisy OLSA sets and tested with 120 noisy OLSA sentences which are also part of the training set. Further, acoustic environment and spatial condition are matched between training and test data. FADE therefore represents an intrusive modeling approach that is different from normal ASR (for which training/testing data are usually disjunct). For SRT estimation, each SNR-specific GMM/HMM combination is tested with sentences at SNRs from -24 dB to 6 dB, from which the SRTs of the SNR-specific systems are obtained. The best (lowest) SRT is used as the global SRT of the entire model for the current acoustic condition.

2.7.2. Baseline models part II

Since a binaural non-intrusive model for predicting SRTs does not exist to the best of our knowledge, the intrusive modified binaural short-time objective intelligibility (MBSTOI) (Andersen et al., 2018) is used as baseline for the second part of this study. The MBSTOI produces accurate SI predictions in different acoustic scenes and has been applied in a large number of studies in the context of SI and hearing aids (Graetzer et al., 2021). The SI predictions are made essentially in the same way as for the short-time objective intelligibility (STOI) (Taal et al., 2011) by using the cross-correlation between the power envelopes of the 1/3 octave bands of a clean speech signal and a degraded signal. To account for binaural effects, both the clean speech and the degraded signal are processed with an EC stage before the envelopes are extracted. The parameters of the EC stage are optimized to maximize the model output with the constraint that the optimization is limited by adding uncorrelated noise to represent limited human performance. This range needs to be mapped to a reference condition to obtain a SI prediction in percent. In this study, the SON0 condition of each language is used as reference. To calculate the BILD, the SON90 condition needs to be predicted twice, i.e., with both ears and with the better ear (BE) only. The BE listening is modeled by deactivating the EC stage and calculating the MBSTOI for each ear separately. The larger value is chosen as result of the BE.

3. Results

3.1. Sampling of the psychometric function

To quantify the number of utterances used for sampling the psychometric function (c.f. Section 2.6), the model prediction error (in terms of the RMSE) was determined as a function of the number of equally spaced SNR bins (ranging from -40 to 20 dB) and the number of matrix sentences per SNR bin. For the SNR range we considered for sampling, we did not observe a strong interaction between these factors and found the total number of utterances to be the major factor for prediction accuracy. Fig. 4 shows the RMSE over the total number of utterances, i.e., the results for a different number of SNR bins/sentences per bin have been pooled. Based on the results of this sub-study, the number of utterances and SNRs used for the predictions of the study parts A and B are selected. The total number of utterances is set to 1400, since doubling this number (which corresponds to doubling the computational cost) only leads to a slightly higher accuracy (0.04 dB lower RMSE).

3.2. Results part I

The results of study Part I are shown in Fig. 5 for the three room conditions. The gray area marks the standard deviation of the subjective data. Most of the PHOBI predictions (21 out of 24) are within the standard deviation of the subjects, with comparable accuracy across rooms. In contrast, the accuracy of BSIM+SII, BAPSI and bBSIM+FADE is noticeably worse for one of the rooms than for the others. To compare the different models, the corresponding RMSEs and correlation coefficients are shown in Table 2.

For each room condition, the lowest RMSE (between 0.3 and 0.6 dB) is produced by one of the intrusive baseline models (BSIM+SII for *Cafeteria*, BAPSI for *Anechoic* and bBSIM+FADE for *Office*), but also a high RMSE for one of the other rooms (between 1.8 and 2.6 dB). PHOBI achieves the lowest RMSE on average and shows similar prediction accuracy across all room conditions with RMSEs ranging from 0.7 dB to 1.0 dB. This is consistent with the Pearson correlation coefficients (with the exception that bBSIM+FADE and PHOBI both achieve the best value for condition *Anechoic*).

Fig. 4. Number of utterances used for calculating the psychometric function and the resulting root mean squared error (RMSE) of the prediction of the speech recognition threshold.

Fig. 5. Speech recognition thresholds (SRTs) of different prediction models in three different room conditions compared to measured SRTs (Beutelmann and Brand, 2006). All predictions are produced for the noise angles shown on the x-axis, but are shifted slightly for improved readability.

3.3. Results part II

The results of the second part of this study in terms of ILD and BILD measurements and predictions are displayed in figure6. ILD and BILD results are broken down into values obtained for the noise located at the right or left side, respectively. Since a virtual anechoic room was used for subjective measurements, differences in subjective data arise from the test-retest variability which is also influenced by the random selection of sentences. This last factor also has a very small effect on model predictions for the L and R conditions. Generally, the intrusive MBSTOI and the proposed non-intrusive model achieve a similar prediction performance: All BILD predictions as well as ILD predictions for the British test are within the standard deviation of the subjective measurements. However, the benefit of the spatial source separation with binaural hearing (ILD) is underestimated for German and Swedish with

Fig. 6. Measurement and prediction results of the intelligibility level difference (ILD) and the binaural intelligibility level difference (BILD), divided into left and right according to the azimuth angle of the noise source. The median of the subjects' results is represented as horizontal line within each box.

Table 2

Root mean squared errors (RMSE) and Pearson correlation values of the SRT predictions from multiple models for three different room conditions. The p-values associated with the correlation denote the significance level.

		Anechoic	Office	Cafeteria	Overall
BSIM+SII	RMSE	1.8 dB	0.5 dB	0.3 dB	1.1 dB
	<i>r</i>	0.95**	0.69	0.98***	0.94***
BAPSI	RMSE	0.6 dB	0.8 dB	2.1 dB	1.3 dB
	<i>r</i>	0.98***	0.74*	0.98***	0.94***
bBSIM+FADE	RMSE	2.6 dB	0.4 dB	0.5 dB	1.6 dB
	<i>r</i>	1.0***	0.88**	0.93**	0.94***
PHOBI	RMSE	1.0 dB	0.7 dB	0.8 dB	0.9 dB
	<i>r</i>	1.0***	0.86*	0.95**	0.97***

* $p < 0.05$.

** $p < 0.01$.

*** $p < 0.001$.

both PHOBI and MBSTOI. Overall, both models are able to predict binaural effects quite well, which is reflected in the RMSEs (PHOBI: 1.5 dB, MBSTOI: 1.1 dB) and the correlation coefficients (PHOBI: 0.95, MBSTOI: 0.96).

4. Discussion

4.1. Discussion part I

The results in Section 3.2 show that the proposed PHOBI model produces the highest prediction accuracy when averaging over acoustic conditions, reflected in low RMSE and high correlation values for the acoustic conditions under consideration. This model therefore seems to be a good choice if information about the acoustic scene is not available, since it appears to generalize well to other scenarios and does not produce strong prediction outliers. However, if a prediction model should only be used for a specific acoustic room condition, one of the baseline models seems to be the best choice (BSIM+SII for Cafeteria, bBSIM+FADE for Office and BAPSI for Anechoic). Due on the nature of the metrics used in this paper (SRT values obtained from dynamically changes of the SNR, from which RMSE values are obtained), statistical tests that take into account all individual data points on sentence level are not applicable. When comparing the SRT values in Figure 5 between models with Wilcoxon signed rank tests the differences are not statistically significant. However, this comparison is based on eight data points only and therefore does not reflect the large amount of data considered in the experiments.

Compared to other modeling approaches, PHOBI drops several requirements of a priori knowledge such as ground truth word labels (required for the ASR-based approach BAPSI) or separately available speech and noise signals (required by several baseline models). Since it predicts the SRT, it does require estimates of the psychometric function, which in turn implies that utterances with known SNR are available. The same is true for determining the SRT of human listeners, where the process of estimating the psychometric function is different from the sampling applied here (see below), but the same kind of signal knowledge is required. PHOBI is therefore not suited for predicting SRT values in arbitrary real-life conditions. For future applications such as model-based

selection of the optimal processing strategy in a hearing device (where *optimal* could relate to the best intelligibility) the model could still be applied by just comparing the MTD values of two competing processing strategies and choosing the algorithm that produces a higher MTD. For short observation windows, this selection could be quite noisy, so the temporal integration time for making such a choice should be investigated in future research.

To use the model in a future hearing device, the integration of a hearing loss simulation would be required. This could be done by adding threshold simulating noise to the extracted features before they are used as input to the DNN. The integration has already been implemented in a monaural SI model (Roßbach et al., 2022), but its use in a binaural model remains to be investigated.

The binaural enhancement stage resulted in a good match with subjective data across rooms and maskers from different azimuth angles when using a single reference condition only (SON0 in Condition *Anechoic* with different speech material). Since training our model incorporated a large variety of noise sources and different sources of reverberation (without noise- or room-specific training), this indicates that the approach might generalize to other unseen conditions as well. The masker for the experiments was a spatially localized, stationary speech-shaped noise, which is clinically the most relevant noise type. It remains to be seen if the model produces accurate SRT estimates for other room conditions and for other masker types (for which in this study subjective data was unavailable). Probably the performance of the binaural stage could be further improved by considering a phone-specific threshold for the chance probability p_c instead of using $p_c = 1/41$ (which was chosen to limit the number of assumptions).

4.2. Discussion part II

The aim of this part is the prediction of the ILD and BILD showing the relative changes between two listening conditions (SON0 and SON90 or monaural SON90 and binaural SON90).

Importance of interaural parameters: ILD and BILD were accurately predicted with PHOBI (RMSE = 1.5 dB), i.e., with a similar accuracy as MBSTOI (RMSE = 1.1 dB), which has access to the narrow-band envelopes of clean and noisy signals. MBSTOI could therefore exploit binaural cues such as interaural time difference ITD_B and interaural level difference ILD_B (the subscript B has been added to avoid confusion with intelligibility level difference). PHOBI could not exploit these important binaural cues directly, but we assume they are at least partially exploited implicitly: A different ILD_B for the left and right ear would be reflected in cleaner phone activations for the ear that is nearer to a desired speech source. ITD_B could not be learned during the training process: The input features of PHOBI are calculated based on spectra from 10-ms segments of speech, and there is no binaural interaction during training. Brungart and Iyer (2012) showed that better-ear glimpsing has a similar effect on the SI than the binaural processing of humans even without using the ITD_B . Instead of using this glimpsing in the time-frequency domain of the audio signals, PHOBI uses better-ear glimpsing on the phone level. While the glimpsing is applied on a different processing level, our results are consistent with the finding from Brungart and Iyer (2012) that effective binaural models do not necessarily require explicit ITD_B coding.

ILD and BILD prediction: The PHOBI prediction error for BILD was lower on average (RMSE of 0.7 dB) compared to ILD (RMSE = 2.0 dB), which arises from the underestimation of ILD values, i.e., the model does not profit as much as human listeners when moving from SON0 to SON90. A possible explanation for this is that the binaural processing stage of the model over- or underestimates one of the conditions used to calculate the ILD and BILD. The monaural SON90 condition implies that no binaural processing is performed, so the SI prediction is not influenced by the binaural stage. Since the BILD estimation produces an RMSE of less than 1 dB, the binaural processing stage of the model appears to be a good approach for the binaural SON90 condition. We therefore assume that the SI of the SON0 condition is overestimated by the model for the specific room conditions subject to Part II, i.e., the model could exploit information from the left and right channel to an extent that humans cannot, since information in both channels should be very similar in the SON0 condition.

Language-specific predictions: The PHOBI prediction performance for the three languages investigated is relatively similar: The RMSE for German, Swedish and British is 1.3 dB, 2.1 dB, and 0.7 dB, respectively. This is despite the fact that the DNN in the PHOBI model was trained with US-English only and it is not adapted to language-specific phone sets. This is an encouraging result for across-language modeling based on phone classification since finding resources for larger models can be difficult, especially for languages that have not been in the focus for commercial or research applications. We assume that prediction performance for other (for instance tonal) languages might suffer and that a retraining of the artificial network is required in these cases. It would be very interesting to explore multi-language training for generalized phone sets and test the model on a larger variety of languages. However, this also requires extensive listening tests in other languages and therefore a larger experimental effort. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the experiments regarding language dependency were based on existing data with only five German and Swedish listeners, respectively. Although the matrix test was designed to obtain a steep psychometric function (and hence accurate estimates of the SRT), it is possible that language-specific differences are not evident from the data presented in Figure 6. However, given the properties of the matrix tests, we presume these effects should be relatively small.

4.3. General discussion

To explore why the deep-learning model performs better than several intrusive approaches, (Spille and Meyer, 2017) analyzed the relevance of input features for correct classification (based on a monaural version of the model introduced in this paper). The analysis showed that the DNN applied listening strategies similar to human listening, in this case, listening in the dips (i.e., focusing on noise “valleys” in modulated noise). We assume such strategies are also used in the current model. Additionally, we assume the explicit use of binaural information that goes beyond better-ear listening to be beneficial in spatial acoustic scenes.

The growing influence of deep-learning models is reflected by the advent of machine learning challenges for SI prediction (e.g. the Clarity Challenges (Graetzer et al., 2021)). All of these models are based on many design decisions and parameter value settings that affect model performance. Often these decisions are the result of experimentation, researcher experience, literature and sometimes luck. As the number of models and studies increases, these decisions can be made more confidently, resulting in more accurate model predictions. Another point that is likely to lead to even more accurate SI prediction models are the developments in the field of speech recognition, such as Whisper (Radford et al., 2023), the SpeechBrain toolkit (Ravanelli et al., 2021) or other of end-to-end systems.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we proposed a model for speech intelligibility prediction in binaural scenes, which is based on phone classification with a deep neural network and referred to as PHOBI. The model quantifies the quality of phone representations and features a binaural integration stage to model the beneficial effect of binaural hearing. The target metric is the SRT, which was compared to different subjective data obtained from normal-hearing listeners: In the first part of the study, PHOBI predictions are compared to SRTs in different rooms and various spatial configurations of target speech and maskers. While baseline models provided better predictions for specific rooms conditions, the best average predictions were obtained with PHOBI. The second part of the study explored the effects of intelligibility level difference (ILD) and binaural ILD for three different languages. PHOBI produced similar results as human listeners (with an RMSE of 1.5 dB between subjective data and model prediction) which was slightly worse than the baseline (RMSE of 1.1 dB). In contrast to all baseline systems considered in the study, our approach is non-intrusive and does not require separate speech or noise signals or access to the true word labels.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jana Roßbach: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Kirsten C. Wagener:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Bernd T. Meyer:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

Acknowledgments

This work was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under Germany's Excellence Strategy – EXC 2177/1 - Project ID 390895286 and by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – Project-ID 352015383 – SFB 1330 C4 and C6. The authors want to thank Thomas Brand and David Hülsmeier for sharing their data and Steven van de Par for his inspiring ideas.

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